

UDL-Informed Checklist

for the Design and Evaluation of AI Chatbots in Education

Authors

Francesca Raffi · Laura Fedeli

University of Macerata (Italy)

Version 1.0 | 2026

Recommended citation

Raffi, F., & Fedeli, L. (2026). UDL-Informed Checklist for the Design and Evaluation of AI Chatbots in Education (Version 1.0). University of Macerata. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18184801>

Reuse and Attribution

This checklist is openly available for educational and research purposes. Users are encouraged to use, adapt and further develop the framework in different disciplinary and institutional contexts. When using or adapting this checklist, please acknowledge the original UDL-Informed Checklist by citing the Zenodo record (DOI above).

Introduction

These guidelines build upon the principles of the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) Guidelines 3.0 (CAST, 2024) and are intended to support the design and evaluation of accessible and inclusive AI-powered chatbots for educational contexts.

They provide a practical framework to support the design, implementation, evaluation, and continuous improvement of chatbot-based language learning environments. The checklist promotes learner engagement, accessibility, learner agency, and knowledge transfer while addressing barriers rooted in exclusion and bias. Each guideline is further articulated through specific evaluation criteria.

Guideline 1. Ensure Engagement

1. Autonomy and Self-Efficacy

- Chatbots provide options for choice and autonomy in content, tools, assessment opportunities and timing.
- Learners can choose the direction of the conversation according to their needs.
- Tasks encourage active participation and self-reflection.
- Feedback promotes perseverance, self-efficacy, self-awareness and goal achievement.
- The chatbot supports learners experiencing frustration or anxiety.
- Learners progressively develop coping strategies and confidence.

2. Relevance and Meaningfulness

- Learners make meaningful choices aligned with personal goals.
- Activities are flexible and adaptable to learners' interests.
- Tasks foster purposeful learning.
- Learners feel valued and safe to engage.
- Relevant examples support goal visualisation.
- Outputs adapt to learners' linguistic competence.
- Feedback is specific and action-oriented.

3. Motivation

- Multiple means of engagement are provided.
- The chatbot supports learner choice.
- Creativity and imagination are encouraged.
- The environment promotes playfulness.
- Learners do not feel judged.
- Gamification can be implemented.
- Effort and commitment are reinforced.
- Progress is valued over innate ability.

Guideline 2. Ensure Representation

1. Diversity

- Learner diversity is recognised.
- Text-to-speech options are available.
- Key information is presented through multiple means.
- Vocabulary and language are clarified on request.
- The chatbot can repeat and paraphrase information.
- Linguistic and cultural diversity is respected.
- Multiple ways of acquiring knowledge are supported.

2. Display of Information

- The interface is flexible, accessible and customisable.
- Users can adjust fonts, spacing, colours, contrast and other interface features.

Guideline 3. Ensure Knowledge Transfer

1. Customized Support

- Learning preferences are valued.
- Graduated support is provided.
- Differentiated feedback and authentic examples are offered.
- The chatbot supports progress monitoring and long-term learning.

2. Connections with Prior Knowledge

- Prior knowledge is connected to new learning.
- Information is presented logically.
- Learners' backgrounds are valued.
- Knowledge can be transferred to authentic contexts.

About this checklist

This checklist operationalises the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL) for the design and evaluation of AI chatbots in educational settings. It draws on the UDL Guidelines 3.0 (CAST, 2024) while integrating evidence from research on chatbot usability, accessibility, conversational design, and inclusive educational technologies.

Bibliography

- Borsci, S., Malizia, A., Schmettow, M., van der Velde, F., Tariverdiyeva, G., Balaji, D., & Chamberlain, A. (2022). The chatbot usability scale: The design and pilot of a usability scale for interaction with AI-based conversational agents. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 26, 95–119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00779-021-01582-9>
- CAST. (2024). *Universal Design for Learning Guidelines 3.0*. <https://udlguidelines.cast.org/>
- Johari, N. M., & Nohuddin, P. N. (2021). Quality attributes for a good chatbot: A literature review. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology*, 12(7), 109–119.
- Mateos-Sanchez, M., Casado Melo, A., Sánchez Blanco, L., & Feroso García, A. M. (2022). Chatbot as educational and inclusive tool for people with intellectual disabilities. *Sustainability*, 14(3), Article 1520. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031520>
- Meyer, A., Rose, D. H., & Gordon, D. (2014). *Universal design for learning: Theory and practice*. CAST Professional Publishing.
- Novak, K. (2021). *UDL now! A teacher's Monday-to-Friday guide to implementing Universal Design for Learning (2nd ed.)*. CAST Professional Publishing.

- Rao, K., Ok, M. W., & Bryant, B. R. (2014). A review of research on Universal Design educational models. *Remedial and Special Education, 35*(3), 153–166. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741932513518980>
- Silva, G. R. S., & Canedo, E. D. (2024). Towards user-centric guidelines for chatbot conversational design. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction, 40*(2), 98–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2022.2118244>
- Stanley, J., ten Brink, R., Valiton, A., Bostic, T., & Scollan, R. (2022). Chatbot accessibility guidance: A review and way forward. In X.-S. Yang et al. (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Sixth International Congress on Information and Communication Technology (Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, Vol. 216, pp. 919–942)*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-1781-2_80
-

Contact and Collaboration

The authors welcome feedback, implementation reports, validation studies, and adaptations of the checklist in different educational and disciplinary contexts.

Corresponding author

Francesca Raffi

Department of Humanities, University of Macerata (Italy)
f.raffi@unimc.it